

Optimizing miniature phase change cells for in-process self-validating thermocouples

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Abstract

Thermocouples are widely used in industry for process temperature measurement and control. Calibration drift is a well-known problem which adversely affects process control, particularly in harsh environments (e.g. high temperature). To overcome this, a mechanism for self-calibration of thermocouples has been developed (tradename 'INSEVA') which makes use of a miniature phase change cell. The cell is located within the thermocouple assembly, near the measurement junction (i.e. the tip), so that when melting occurs, the temperature is held constant for a short time, enabling *in-situ* calibration. The cell contains less than 1 gram of phase change material, and the temperature is measured outside the cell. This makes the measurement sensitive to ambient conditions, so great care is needed over the design to enable robust, practical operation. We describe a COMSOL model to optimize the design and use of the self-validating thermocouple.

Keywords: Temperature measurement; thermometry; self-validation; SI traceability; heat transfer

Introduction

Thermocouples are widely used in industry for process temperature measurement and control. Calibration drift is a well-known problem which adversely affects process control, particularly in harsh environments (e.g. high temperature, contamination, ionizing radiation, etc.). To overcome this, a mechanism for self-calibration of thermocouples has been developed which makes use of a miniature phase change cell which contains an ingot of metal or alloy [1,2]. The phase change cell is located within the thermocouple assembly, near the measurement junction (i.e. the tip), so that when melting occurs, the temperature is held constant for a short time. Since the melting temperature is known, the thermocouple can be calibrated *in situ*.

The cell is very small, containing less than 1 gram of phase change material, so great care is needed over the design to enable the detection of a robust, observable melting plateau. There are several subtleties associated with the practical realization of this technique, the most significant being the fact that the measurement junction is displaced from the phase change cell, not embedded within it, so that during melting its temperature is some weighted average of the melting temperature and the ambient temperature. This means that the indicated melting temperature depends on the ambient temperature, which is undesirable – it should be invariant. It is of great interest to identify the part of the melting

curve which is independent of the ambient temperature; this is most likely to be in the initial part of the melting process when the ambient temperature is close to the melting temperature. It is also of interest to examine the sensitivity of the device to various parameters in order to optimize it.

In this paper, the geometry and physics of the system are introduced, and how these are implemented in COMSOL. The results of the simulation are then presented, starting with an investigation of the relationship between the melting curves and the true melting temperature for various ambient temperature-time profiles. The melting of metal-carbon alloys is studied, because this is much less well understood than that of pure metals (the former has a much wider melting range than the latter). The study then moves on to various optimization studies, including the effect of mechanical thermal isolation of the cell, effect of modelling the air within the thermocouple assembly using computational fluid dynamics (rather than treating it as static), and the effect of coating the phase change cell with different emissivity material. The paper concludes with a summary of the studies.

Simulation

The geometry is shown in Figure 1. Specifically, the end of the thermocouple is shown, although the whole assembly is 700 mm long. The outer protective sheath and the inner twin-bore sheath are both made of 99.7 % pure recrystallized alumina. The thermocouple wires are made of platinum (in

reality, one wire is made of platinum and one wire is made of a platinum-rhodium alloy, typically 10 % or 13 % rhodium by weight). The two wires are attached to the lid of a cylindrical graphite crucible, and the graphite makes the electrical connection between them. The point at which the wires meet the graphite comprises the measurement junction, and it is the temperature of this that the thermocouple measures. Inside the graphite crucible is an ingot of phase change material, which can be either a pure metal (typically used below 1084 °C [3,4]) or a metal-carbon alloy (for use above this temperature [5]). The space within the outer protective sheath is filled with argon.

Figure 1. COMSOL geometry of the measuring end of the self-validating thermocouple. The outer protective ceramic sheath is filled with argon gas. The entire assembly has an outer diameter of 7 mm and a length of 700 mm. Note the displaced measurement junction.

There are two principal, distinct modes of operation. 1) The temperature starts at one stable temperature slightly (a few degrees) below the melting temperature of the phase change cell, then is ramped up to another stable temperature slightly above the melting temperature, to facilitate the melting. 2) The temperature is continuously ramping up, starting several tens of degrees below the melting temperature, passing through the melting temperature, and ending several tens of degrees above. The shape of the melting curve is very different in the two cases.

What makes the use of this design challenging is that the thermocouple measurement junction (where the wires are connected) is outside the phase change cell – not immersed within it – so the temperature measured by the thermocouple represents some weighted average of the melting temperature and the ambient temperature outside the thermocouple. In practice this means that the measured melting curve has characteristics (such as slope and temperature offset) that depend on the ambient temperature and its rate of increase. That is of

course highly undesirable if this phase change cell is to be used as an invariant temperature reference for re-calibration of the thermocouple. The aim of the model is to enable a link to be established between the melting curve and the true melting temperature of the ingot. Specifically, the aim is to identify any features of the melting curve which signify melting onset, and which are invariant with respect to temperature.

The simulation is carried out using a three-dimensional time dependent heat transfer in fluids and solids model. Since the temperature range of interest is above 950 °C, all internal surfaces (i.e. within the outer sheath) are radiatively coupled using the surface-to-surface heat transfer interface. All surfaces were modelled with the ‘diffuse surface’ interface. The emissivity was taken to be independent of wavelength and is 0.3 for platinum, 0.7 for alumina and 0.95 for graphite.

The thermal interaction between the outer sheath and the environment is modelled by specifying the ambient temperature for the outer diffuse surface; either with a sigmoid function to transition from the lower to the upper temperature, or with the product of the time and the rate of change of temperature, as required. Additionally, a sigmoid function is used to describe the variation of temperature along the entire length of the thermocouple (hot at the measurement end, 20 °C at the cold end). To check the dominance of radiative heat transfer, a realistic convective heat transfer boundary condition was applied to the outer surface of the sheath as well, which made an insignificant difference.

The phase change was modelled using a Heaviside function within the phase change material interface. For the pure metal, silver was chosen (melting temperature approximately 961.78 °C) with a melting temperature range of 0.01 °C. For the high temperature metal-carbon alloy, cobalt-carbon was chosen (melting temperature approximately 1324 °C) with a melting temperature range of 0.1 °C. As the weight fraction of carbon is very small, the bulk properties of the metal were used.

The default settings were used for the solver, except that a relative tolerance of 10^{-8} was necessary to model the pure metal due to its very narrow melting temperature range, while 10^{-6} was sufficient for the alloy. It was necessary to enforce the time stepping taken by the solver with the ‘strict’ setting to avoid missing the melting entirely. The default physics-controlled mesh was used with ‘normal’ element size.

Simulation Results

The temperature distribution within the assembly during melting of the phase change material is shown in Figure 2. This exemplifies the operation of the device; the melting holds the temperature of the phase change cell constant, enabling the *in-situ* re-calibration of the thermocouple. However, Figure 2 also shows that the measurement junction (where the wires are connected to the end of the graphite cylinder) is at a higher temperature than the cell. This is further evident in Figure 3 for the case where the surrounding ambient temperature transitions from one temperature to another. It can be seen that the slope and offset of the thermocouple depends on the surrounding temperature. This is not desirable for a device which needs to provide an invariant temperature, so a series of simulations have been performed to enable analysis of the melting curves in order to extract any features which are independent of the ambient temperature or rate of temperature increase.

Figure 2. Surface plot of the self-validating thermocouple during melting. Color represents temperature. Note the measurement junction where the thermocouple wires are attached to the top of the graphite cell is considerably warmer than the phase change material.

Constant ambient temperature offset

In the case where the temperature is held constant at some temperature below T_m , then increased to some temperature above T_m to induce the melt, the transition between the two temperatures as a function of time is achieved by specifying the ambient temperature as a function of time by using a sigmoid function. This is the temperature assigned to the radiative heat transfer ‘ambient temperature’ boundary condition on the outside surface of the sheath surrounding the assembly (see Figure 2). The resulting melting curves for three different furnace offsets (the offset is the difference between the ambient temperature and T_m) is shown in the top panel of Figure 3.

Figure 3. Melting curves (of a metal-carbon alloy) expressed as temperature, indicated temperature, T , as a function of time, t (top). Middle and bottom panels show dt/dT and d^2t/dT^2 respectively, as a function of T . Note in the top panel the indicated temperature is always higher than the true melting temperature. In the bottom panel it is evident that the true melting temperature (1324°C) coincides with the point of inflection (i.e. where $d^2t/dT^2 = 0$) of the melting curve shown at top.

To seek features which are characteristic of the onset of melting, the first and second derivatives, dt/dT and d^2t/dT^2 , are shown as a function of temperature indicated by the thermocouple in the

middle and bottom panels, respectively, of [Figure 3](#). Most interestingly, the bottom panel of [Figure 3](#) demonstrates that the onset of melting, which does not depend on the furnace offset¹, coincides with the point of inflection² (where $d^2t/dT^2 = 0$) between the initial steady temperature and T_m .

Constant ambient temperature ramp rate

In the case where the ambient temperature is continuously ramping upwards, the situation is somewhat clearer. [Figure 4](#) shows the melting curves for three different ramp rates. In this case the onset of melting is clearly visible as the point where the gradient, dt/dT changes abruptly, and is evidently the point which does not depend on the ramp rate³. In practical terms, this point may be detected using conventional change detection algorithms, or by fitting of piecewise linear functions.

Figure 4. Melting curve for the case where the ambient temperature is continuously ramping upwards; three different temperature ramp rates are shown.

Thermal isolation of the cell

A key feature of the self-validating thermocouple assembly is mechanical robustness. The point where the thermocouple is attached to the lead-in wires can be delicate, so a central portion of the twin-bore insulator (left part of [Figure 2](#)) is extruded in order to abut the miniature phase-change cell, thereby minimizing the strain on the wires. However, this has the potential to increase the thermal contact between the cell and the twin-bore ceramic tube, which, given the tiny amount of metal in the cell, could degrade the metrological performance by shortening the melting duration. The extent to which this is a problem was evaluated by progressively distancing the abutting part of the

twin-bore insulator from the cell. In can be seen in [Figure 5](#) that the heat load introduced by this abutment is in fact minimal.

Figure 5. Melting curve for the case where the rectangular twin-bore ceramic extension abuts the fixed-point cell, and where it is progressively distanced.

Amount of cell filled with the ingot

In general, the more metal there is in the ingot, the longer the duration of the melting plateau, which yields a higher quality calibration. Because of the geometry of the system, partially filling the cell means that the metal is both smaller in quantity, and is displaced further from the measurement junction, which can be particularly problematic. The effect of only partially filling the ingot was investigated, and the melting plateau is shown in [Figure 6](#) for different filling fractions. It can be seen that the filling fraction has quite a substantial effect on the quality of the melting plateau, which indicates that great care should be taken to maximize it.

Figure 6. Melting curves for different filling fractions of the cell, as indicated.

¹ That is, it is invariant.

² Or at least, it is very close.

³ This is because at the start of melting the temperature of the thermocouple measurement junction, the ambient temperature, and the melting temperature of the ingot are all the same.

Effect of airflow within the assembly

The original model was set up so that heat transfer between all the surfaces is only by radiative heat transfer, which is a reasonable assumption because most operation is at relatively high temperatures, where drift is a problem (i.e. above approximately 900 °C). However, to investigate whether airflow within the assembly is significant, laminar flow was modelled in the interior air domain, including buoyancy (thermocouple is vertically oriented). A 'coarse' mesh was needed to obtain a melting plateau of adequate quality. Figure 7 shows that it does not make a significant difference whether the air is flowing or not, presumably due to the very small size of the interior space, which greatly impedes convection.

Figure 7. Melting curve with and without CFD (i.e. whether or not the air within the assembly is described by buoyancy-driven laminar flow, or is static).

Effect of coating on the graphite cell

The original model assumed the graphite phase change cell was uncoated, but given that the main heat transfer mechanism is radiative, it is of interest to understand the effect of emissivity of any coating of the cell. An emissivity of 0.3 (representative of typical metallic coating materials) was employed. It can be seen in Figure 8 that the emissivity does have a moderate effect on the duration of the melting plateau, with lower emissivity of 0.3 (compared with 0.95 for graphite) extending the duration by approximately 25 %.

Figure 8. Melting curves for two different values of the emissivity on the outer surface of the cylindrical fixed-point cell. Lower emissivity appears to be beneficial, resulting in approximately 25 % longer melting duration.

Conclusions

A series of studies of the behaviour of self-validating thermocouples has been performed using COMSOL. Simulation is extremely useful for this system because such studies are too difficult to perform reliably and systematically by performing experiments due to the inability to control or measure the influencing parameters with sufficient precision. The simulation enables some general conclusions to be drawn about the design and operation of the self-validating thermocouple, by investigating:

- The effect of different temperature-time profiles on the melting curve (i.e. ambient temperature and rate of temperature increase) and how to determine the point on the curve which is independent of those ambient thermal effects
- The effect of using phase change materials comprising metal-carbon alloys (which have a wider melting temperature range than pure metals).
- The effect of thermally decoupling the phase change cell from the rest of the assembly to maximize melt duration and minimize other thermal perturbations
- The effect of varying how much of the cell is filled with the phase change material
- The effect of airflow within the self-validating thermocouple assembly
- The effect of coating the phase change cell with a material of different emissivity

The NPL-designed self-validating thermocouple is in the process of being commercialized by CCPI Europe under the trade name INSEVA [1]. It is

currently being trialed in high value heat treatment processes in the UK and Europe; the improvements in process temperature control by eliminating calibration drift mean better energy efficiency, better product consistency and yield, reduced noxious emissions and improved overall measurement assurance.

The modelling described in this paper will feed into future iterations of the design and operating principles.

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